

A Machine Learning Approach for Predicting and Analyzing Traffic Collision Severity to
Enhance Road Safety

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0. Abstract

Road traffic injuries remain a leading cause of death globally, particularly among young people. With the advent of self-driving cars aiming to reduce these statistics, concerns about their risk management capabilities and decision-making algorithms persist. This study explores factors influencing crash severity, focusing on the role of collision type. Utilizing data from the California Highway Patrol's SWITRS database (2006–2021), we analyzed 260,000 crashes, employing data cleaning, one-hot encoding, and oversampling to address categorical variables and imbalance ((P. Mayich. Car crashes California 2006–2021. *Kaggle Dataset*. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/petermayich/car-crashes-california-2006-2021> (2024).)). Exploratory analysis highlighted motorcycle collisions, pedestrian actions, and bicycle collisions as significant predictors of severity.

To predict and model crash severity, we implemented k-nearest neighbors (KNN), neural networks, and random forest classifiers. While the neural network faced challenges with imbalanced data, the random forest model achieved the highest weighted accuracy (71%), effectively handling categorical variables. Feature importance analysis confirmed collision type's significant role, alongside unexpected factors like motorcycle involvement. Ethical considerations regarding bias, safety, and potential misuse were addressed to ensure responsible model application.

Our findings emphasize the correlation between collision type and crash severity, offering insights to enhance self-driving algorithms. By integrating these results, autonomous vehicles can improve decision-making in high-risk scenarios, advancing safety and minimizing crash outcomes. Future research should address data distribution challenges and explore applicability across diverse geographies and traffic conditions.

Keywords: Traffic accidents, self-driving cars, collision severity, machine learning, random forest classifier, crash prediction.

1. Introduction

According to the World Health Organization, road traffic injuries remain the leading killer of children and young people aged 5-29 years ((World Health Organization. Global status report on road safety 2023. *World Health Organization*. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/375016/9789240086517-eng.pdf?sequence=1> (2023).)). While several regulations have been put in place to try and minimize this figure, the issue of traffic accidents has persisted. This has led to the rise of self-driving cars, where algorithms analyze several driving factors and attempt to make the most optimal decision for driver safety. However, this is accompanied by several concerns, such as risk management and faulty algorithms. These issues motivated further research into how self-driving algorithms make the “right” decisions, and what outcome they prioritize in a crash. Our research investigates the

factors these algorithms consider in high-risk scenarios, and specifically, how the type of collision can influence crash severity, as models need to mitigate risk.

1.1 Related Works

Traffic accidents remain a major issue in the United States, with a fatality rate of 14.01 per every 100,000 registered vehicles in 2022 ((National Highway Traffic Safety Administration. Critical reasons for crashes investigated in the national motor vehicle crash causation survey. *National Highway Traffic Safety Administration*.
<https://crashstats.nhtsa.dot.gov/Api/Public/Publication/812506> (2018).)).

Additionally, in a study conducted by the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, over 40% of crashes can be attributed to a lack of awareness, with an additional 33% due to poor decision-making ((National Highway Traffic Safety Administration. Critical reasons for crashes investigated in the national motor vehicle crash causation survey. *National Highway Traffic Safety Administration*.
<https://crashstats.nhtsa.dot.gov/Api/Public/Publication/812506> (2018).)).

The reduced frequency of environmentally-caused crashes was also alarming, consisting of around 2% of crashes ((National Highway Traffic Safety Administration. Critical reasons for crashes investigated in the national motor vehicle crash causation survey. *National Highway Traffic Safety Administration*.
<https://crashstats.nhtsa.dot.gov/Api/Public/Publication/812506> (2018).)). While self-driving cars have been developed as a response to these alarming figures, they still lack the consciousness and decisiveness to be considered a viable option for reducing crash frequency and severity.

In a paper by Đorđe Petrović, he discusses the benefits and limitations of implementing autonomous vehicles on the road ((Đ. Petrović, S. Nikolić, and M. Pešić. Traffic accidents with autonomous vehicles: Type of collisions, manoeuvres, and errors of conventional vehicles' drivers. *Transportation Research Procedia*, **45**, 161–168 (2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.03.003>)).

The main advantages were the reduction of pedestrian and broadside collisions since self-driving vehicles have greater road awareness and faster responses to obstacles ((Đ. Petrović, S. Nikolić, and M. Pešić. Traffic accidents with autonomous vehicles: Type of collisions, manoeuvres, and errors of conventional vehicles' drivers. *Transportation Research Procedia*, **45**, 161–168 (2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.03.003>)).

However, he then explains how these vehicles have different driving patterns, increasing the probability of rear-end collisions ((Đ. Petrović, S. Nikolić, and M. Pešić. Traffic accidents with autonomous vehicles: Type of collisions, manoeuvres, and errors of conventional vehicles' drivers. *Transportation Research Procedia*, **45**, 161–168 (2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.03.003>)). To further analyze this relationship, we decided to look into how the type of collision impacts crash severity, to see how autonomous cars would impact collision outcomes.

Although similar studies have been published such as Bingbing Nie's Human injury-based safety decision of automated vehicles, our study explored a wide variety of predictive approaches beyond the neural network, and rather than analyzing the sedan-to-sedan collision, we generalized our model to all types of vehicles with a much larger dataset (Q. Wang, Q. Zhou, M. Lin, and B. Nie. Human injury-based safety decision of automated vehicles. *iScience*, **25**(8), 104703 (2022).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.104703>)). Beyond just predicting collision severity, we analyzed the most important features that help predict severity.

1.2 Research Questions

This raises the question of what factors influence crash severity, or more specifically; how does the type of collision influence driving severity? Drivers often have to weigh different options when in tense situations, and implementing an algorithm that mimics this decision-making process would greatly improve driving safety and minimize crashes. We hypothesized that the type of collision would have a strong correlation with crash severity, as certain situations tend to be significantly more dangerous than others. However, these predictions were answered early in the modeling stage, raising the question: what other factors influence the level of collision severity, and what modeling method is the most appropriate to predict these relationships?

2. Results

2.1 KNN Model

The first classification model we explored is a k-nearest-neighbors or KNN model. This uses the k nearest data points and makes a majority prediction as to what the classification is. We then scaled down our dataset for visualization purposes and created a heatmap of the majority of labels (Figure 7). This provides a clear picture of how the model classifies and assigns labels to each data point. To pick our k, we decided to use the square root of the elements or rows in our total dataset, which, after cleaning and preprocessing the data is 462 neighbors. The major limitation of this model is the lack of continuous variables. Since all the variables fed into the model are categorical there is no way to calculate distances between points, meaning the ordering of categories within a predictor loses value. The KNN ended up with an accuracy of 66% making it a suboptimal method of prediction, especially when dealing with high-risk scenarios.

2.2 Neural Network

Next, we implemented a neural network to see how it would handle our classification problem. It uses a set of inputs and feeds them into hidden layers, each with a set of neurons that helps build on model complexity. Finally, we obtain a probability vector of the collision severity, where the model takes the highest probability and outputs a prediction. To maximize the accuracy of our model and ensure that it doesn't overfit or underfit, we optimized for the number of hidden layers and neurons in each layer, ensuring that our model accurately captures trends within the data. Using the most optimal hyperparameters, we obtained an accuracy of 64%. However, after visualizing the model's predictions through a confusion matrix, we observed that the model classified every instance as property damage, regardless of its true label (Figure 10). Since the dataset has an uneven distribution of property damage occurrences, the model can "guess" the type of damage, without learning underlying patterns. We decided to modify the model using a MinMax scaler, to remove any complications caused by different scales in our continuous variables. While most of our variables are categorical, implementing a scaler helps to remove feature scale bias, and ensure all continuous variables are treated equally when making predictions. In our updated confusion matrix, we still noticed that our model was "guessing", and rarely predicting outcomes other than property damage, obtaining an accuracy of 66% (Figure 11). Since the distribution of property damage in the dataset is uneven we used a sampling technique called SMOTE where we oversampled underrepresented categories. In the pie chart of our collision severities after SMOTE, all types of severity seem to be balanced equally. This forces the model to "learn" and not guess, since it isn't rewarded for guessing the outcome with

the highest probability without considering any predictors (Figure 13). While we also tried using SMOTE in the random forest model, it was much less receptive to the change and was making extremely inaccurate predictions. Although our confusion matrix shows that the neural network performed worse with SMOTE, it was able to learn patterns in the data, and with more model complexity and variable selection, it could exceed the accuracy before implementing SMOTE (Figure 12).

2.3 Random Forest

Finally, we decided to create a random forest model due to its ability to effectively interpret discrete values and make accurate classifications. Since it averages the insights of multiple decision trees to make a majority prediction, it is more robust and less prone to overfitting. To obtain the highest accuracy, we tuned our hyperparameters using the Scikit-learn GridSearch function, which takes in a pre-defined array of parameters and computes for the most beneficial combination. After training our model using each hyperparameter combination, we obtained an accuracy of 66%. However, when looking at the confusion matrix of our Random Forest Classifier (Figure 4), we noticed that the category “other injury” was frequently misclassified. This was attributed to the variability of the category, since “other injury” isn’t clearly defined. Therefore, we decided to weigh it at 25% of its original weight, as there was a possibility the officer reporting the severity of the crash could not discern the category of severity. Adjusting the weight helped mitigate misclassifications and improved the model’s overall accuracy. Since the 4 categories encompass all types of severity, there is a possibility that “Other Injury” could belong with one of them, which is why we weighted “Other Injury” as 25% of its original weight. This adjustment was aimed at refining the model’s performance rather than altering the underlying data distribution, minimizing bias. This produced a weighted accuracy score of 71%. Next, we printed out our classification report (Figure 6), which gave insights into the accuracy of each category. In our classification report, we looked at the precision, which is the individual accuracy score of our model in each category. We also observed the recall or percentage of true positives. We found that the recall for property damage (0.98) was significantly higher than other categories (0.06-0.18), likely due to the distribution of collision severities in the dataset. To fix this issue we tried implementing SMOTE, to see if the model responded to the changing distribution differently. However, this posed many challenges to the model and inevitably hindered its predictive capabilities. The f1-score helps to identify how well the model performs in a certain category, as it is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, making it an appropriate measure of accuracy. Since the f1 score is significantly higher for property damage than other categories, it reaffirmed our suspicions that the data distribution is influencing our model’s prediction. Then, we looked at support, or the number of occurrences of each category in the dataset. We noticed that property damage makes up the majority of the dataset (64%), explaining our model’s performance in each category.

Finally, we plotted the feature importance of the variables we selected in our model (Figure 5) and confirmed that the variables we plotted on the bar graphs were indeed the most correlated and significant features in predicting crash severity. Feature importance is calculated by looking at how much a certain feature reduces impurity within each split, or contributes to the decision-making process.

3. Discussion

3.1 Model Comparison

In the present investigation, three distinct models were utilized to forecast the severity of crashes: k-nearest neighbors (KNN), neural networks, and a random forest classifier. Each model was selected based on its unique strengths in addressing classification challenges; however, their performance demonstrated considerable variation.

The KNN model, using proximity-based majority voting for classification, achieved an accuracy of 66%. Although simple and interpretable, KNN was not able to handle the categorical nature of the dataset; it is inherently unable to measure distances or assign weights to categories. This made KNN suboptimal in the task of predicting crash severity for high-risk scenarios.

Next, a neural network was implemented to explore its capacity to model non-linear relationships in the data. The model performance had reached a plateau at 66%, even after optimization of hyperparameters and application of techniques like MinMax scaling and SMOTE to handle class imbalance. From the confusion matrix, it was also found that the neural network was biased toward the majority class, property damage only. It did show some ability to learn patterns in the data, but still, its accuracy and reliability were low enough to be applied in real life.

The random forest classifier was the best-performing model. It performed a weighted accuracy of 71% by averaging the predictions from many decision trees and outperformed other models. The random forest handled categorical variables well, being less prone to overfitting. However, the initial misclassifications it had were those within the unclear category of "other injury." Adjusting this in the model by weighting at 25% improved its performance without adding bias to the original distribution of the dataset. Feature importance analysis highlighted that collision type and motorcycle involvement were significant predictors of crash severity, validating the model's decision-making process.

In conclusion, the random forest classifier emerged as the most dependable option, merging resilience and comprehensibility while achieving superior predictive precision. Its capacity to discern significant elements affecting crash severity renders it particularly appropriate for incorporation into algorithms for autonomous vehicles, thereby improving decision-making in scenarios that pose considerable risk. Subsequent research could enhance this model further by tackling issues related to class imbalance and investigating more sophisticated ensemble methodologies.

3.2 Ethical Issues

When using a model that can impact lives, it is important to consider its ethical implications. Firstly, minimizing collision severity based on an incorrect prediction can lead to an unfavorable outcome, potentially harming the passengers in the vehicle. Secondly, if the model is built to optimize passenger safety, it could cause significant harm to others while minimizing injury to passengers. Therefore, we would need an additional decision-making algorithm to help our model identify the most optimal outcome for everyone. Furthermore, identifying and mitigating biases within the data is a key responsibility. Car crash data can reflect broader social inequalities, such as differences in crash rates based on geography, socio-economic status, or demographics. For example, identifying a certain race as more likely to be involved in a crash.

We need to recognize biases and adjust our algorithms to avoid perpetuating or exacerbating existing disparities. Finally, there is a possibility of malicious use, since the ability to minimize crash severity can be used instead to maximize severity. This necessitates extensive cybersecurity and external safety measures to mitigate these scenarios.

3.3 Conclusions and Limitations

After developing our hypothesis, preprocessing the data, and implementing our model, we observed several limitations and failures that need to be addressed before generalizing our results. Firstly, the distribution of data is uneven, and property damage is by far the most likely type of collision severity. This allows the model to essentially "guess" and get the right answer most of the time when we want it to learn. While oversampling, as discussed earlier, could solve this problem, it also can lead to overfitting, among other concerns. Secondly, some predictors, such as bicycle collisions, are less frequent in the dataset, due to a low number of bicycle collisions being severe enough to be reported, limiting their influence in the model's predictions. Furthermore, the data was only collected in California, making it challenging to generalize predictions to other areas, as there are different traffic laws for each state. Finally, to generalize and utilize our results, a higher accuracy and more advanced model is necessary, as self-driving algorithms can't afford to misclassify a crash.

Through our data visualization and predictive analysis, we were able to successfully resolve our initial questions. We can conclude that the type of collision is highly correlated with collision severity, providing an accurate basis to predict crash outcomes. This is due to its high feature importance, with a value of about 0.1, suggesting a low impurity, and aligning with our initial hypothesis. However, other unexpected factors also played a large role in our model predictions, namely, motorcycle collisions. When graphing it against the distribution of collision severity, we noticed a significant difference between collisions involving motorcycles compared to those that didn't.

Next, after utilizing different types of models, we identified a random forest classifier to be the most optimal. Its effective handling of categorical variables, along with its higher accuracy score, made it the most appropriate model for predicting crash severity. While the KNN's accuracy was marginally less, it is not the most effective method when considering classification, since there is no way to weight the model or calculate distance between points.

With our model finalized and optimized for the best hyperparameters, we were able to achieve 71% weighted accuracy in predicting the collision severity. Furthermore, we achieved a 98% recall in predicting the most common collision severity, property damage only, indicating that our model is effective at identifying positive cases for the most common collision severity.

While analyzing car crash footage may prove to be more effective in the case of collision prediction we chose to instead use variables that can be inferred from footage, as many self-driving vehicles have exceptional sensors, but poor decision-making and situational awareness.

By identifying the factors that influence crash severity, particularly the type of collision, we aim to provide insights into crash minimization. These insights can be applied to self-driving

algorithms, providing them with the knowledge necessary to make informed decisions in high-risk scenarios. This capability is essential for predicting potential hazards and enabling timely interventions to avert accidents.

4. Methods

Our study is both observational and experimental, as we do not manipulate any variables but instead observe and analyze the relationships between crash characteristics (such as collision type and vehicle involvement) and crash severity. We also incorporated predictive modeling and used several machine learning algorithms to evaluate its effectiveness in predicting collision severity.

4.1 Exploratory Analysis

Next, we used a heatmap (Figure 3) to visualize the relationship between the chosen explanatory variables compared to the collision severity. Surprisingly, the three most correlated variables were motorcycle collision, pedestrian action, and bicycle collision. This suggested that the severity of the collision was highly correlated with the type of vehicle involved in the crash, while we predicted the type of collision to be a more influential factor. After analyzing our correlation matrix, we decided to plot some of the variable relationships against collision severity. First, we created a shaded bar graph (Figure 1) representing the frequency of different types of collision severity, across types of collision. By observing the graph, we noticed that there were different distributions of collision severity for each type of collision, indicating a possible correlation. These discrepancies aligned with our intuition, as more dangerous types of collisions, such as pedestrian collisions, were correlated with a higher degree of severity, such as fatality. Then, we explored the relationship between motorcycle collisions and collision severity, by plotting another shaded bar graph (Figure 2). In instances where there was a motorcycle collision, there was a much higher likelihood of severe injury and fatality, compared to when there were none, there were less severe types of collisions. Since the distribution of collision severity differed greatly, we were able to determine a significant correlation between motorcycle collision and collision severity. Furthermore, we wanted to analyze the distribution of our response variable, collision severity. We plotted a pie chart of the distributions and discovered that a large proportion of collision severities are property damage only. This uneven distribution can lead to biases in the data, leading us to explore oversampling techniques (Figure 9). Finally, we plotted collision severity against the violation category of the crash, using a bubble chart, so we could explore possible correlations and analyze the distribution of these data points. We discovered that most collisions were a result of speeding, and led to only property damage, aligning with the distribution of collision severities that we explored earlier, and our intuition (Figure 8).

4.2 Data Information and Preprocessing

Our data contains all driving accidents from 2006-2021 in California, collected by the California Highway Patrol and its Statewide Integrated Traffic Records System (SWITRS) ((P. Mayich. Car crashes California 2006–2021. *Kaggle Dataset*.

<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/petermayich/car-crashes-california-2006-2021> (2024)).

Although this data is from a single state, it is still applicable to a broad population of autonomous vehicle users, as there is a large population of self-driving cars in California. Furthermore, it is the most populated state, with ample data to predict crash severity. After we chose our dataset,

we randomly sampled 10% of the data and stored it in a separate file. Since the dataset contains 2.6 million data points of crashes, running a model on the full data would be inefficient and computationally expensive. We decided to sample 10% of the model because we concluded that 260 thousand data points would be sufficient for our model and representative of our full dataset. First, we conducted variable selection, where we used a combination of intuition and plotting. To analyze car crashes, we selected collision severity as our response variable, as we found it to be the most important factor when considering collisions. Collision severity was categorized into 5 factors: property damage only, pain, severe injury, fatal, or other injury. We then selected predictors that we believed would have a strong correlation with collision severity, such as the type of collision and the vehicles involved in the collision. Out of all the 132 variables in our dataset, we chose to use 31 independent variables in our analysis. Next, we printed out the data frame and found that most of the variables, including collision severity, were categorical, ruling out any type of regression model. After taking the desired columns and storing them in a separate data frame, we one-hot encoded the categorical variables. Using a loop, we transformed 'object' variables into integer values, allowing them to be fed into our model. We then binned the continuous variables by running a loop that categorized them into five different bins. Furthermore, many entries contained uninterpretable values, such as NaNs, meaning they had to be dropped from the dataset. Finally, we split our data into 80% training data and 20% testing data, minimizing data leakage and ensuring the model doesn't overestimate accuracy.

Appendix

Figure 1. Shaded bar graph of the frequency of collision severity against the type of collision

Figure 2. Shaded bar graph of the frequency of collision severity against motorcycle collision

Figure 3. Correlation matrix of 31 selected variables

Figure 4: Confusion matrix representing testing data results

Figure 5: Feature importances in the Random Forest model

Classification Report:					
	precision	recall	f1-score	support	
0	0.43	0.07	0.13	443	
1	0.44	0.18	0.26	5776	
2	0.51	0.09	0.15	11514	
3	0.69	0.98	0.81	34210	
4	0.39	0.05	0.09	1489	
accuracy			0.67	53432	
macro avg	0.49	0.28	0.29	53432	
weighted avg	0.61	0.67	0.58	53432	

Figure 6. Classification report of Random Forest

FIGURE 7. KNN heatmap visualization

FIGURE 8. Bubble Chart

Distribution of Collision Severity

FIGURE 9. Pie Chart

FIGURE 10. Neural Network Original Confusion Matrix

FIGURE 11. Neural Network Confusion Matrix with Min Max Scaler

FIGURE 12. Neural Network with SMOTE

Distribution of Collision Severity

FIGURE 13. Validating Data Distribution(Colors consistent with earlier pie chart)

5. References

1. World Health Organization. Global status report on road safety 2023. *World Health Organization*.
<https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/375016/9789240086517-eng.pdf?sequence=1> (2023).
2. National Highway Traffic Safety Administration. Critical reasons for crashes investigated in the national motor vehicle crash causation survey. *National Highway Traffic Safety Administration*. <https://crashstats.nhtsa.dot.gov/Api/Public/Publication/812506> (2018).
3. Đ. Petrović, S. Nikolić, and M. Pešić. Traffic accidents with autonomous vehicles: Type of collisions, manoeuvres, and errors of conventional vehicles' drivers. *Transportation Research Procedia*, **45**, 161–168 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.03.003>.
4. Q. Wang, Q. Zhou, M. Lin, and B. Nie. Human injury-based safety decision of automated vehicles. *iScience*, **25**(8), 104703 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2022.104703>.
5. P. Mayich. Car crashes California 2006–2021. *Kaggle Dataset*.
<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/petermayich/car-crashes-california-2006-2021> (2024).